

Neuroblastoma cases from HULAFE's Paediatric Cancer Collection.

ID: 53e4f28b-432a-4bf9-a7a1-4031ad2eec42

URL: <https://eucaim-node.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/53e4f28b-432a-4bf9-a7a1-4031ad2eec42/details>

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Studies count: 451

Subjects count: 163

Age range: Between 0 years and 15 years

Sex: Female, Male, Undifferentiated, Unkown

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, WHOLEBODY, OTHER, HEAD, SPINE, LIVER, ABDOMENPELVIS, NECK, BONE, HEART, PELVIS, S2 ESTATICA DUAL, KNEE, SKULL, URINARYTRACT, BRAIN, GU MIBG, OPTIC CANAL, CHESTABDOMEN, PANCREAS, TSPINE, LSPINE, TOTAL BODY, HIP, RM ABDOMEN Y_O, ORBIT, TORAX SIN, TUMOR, TORAX, GU TB MIBG I123, SZINTI MIBG, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT, NM, PT